

**IMPACT OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN
LANGUAGE TEACHING**

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the concept of innovative teaching technology, in particular the technology of teaching a foreign language (English) at a non-linguistic university.

In the context of the development of modern means of telecommunications, globalization processes of world society, strengthening intercultural relations, a new approach to defining goals and tasks of modern education at the university. Today, higher education is focused on training a new type of specialist who can effectively apply the theoretical knowledge acquired at the university in practice. The task of a foreign language teacher at a university is not only to develop certain language skills in students, and first of all, the formation and development of communicative and intercultural competencies, the ability to communicate in a foreign language within the framework of real speech interaction.

Key words: innovative technologies, communication, mastering foreign language, interactive teaching methods, computer hardware

Introduction.

Every language reflects the culture of the people who speak it. Therefore, mastering foreign language is inseparable from acquaintance students with the facts of history, culture, social phenomena, and social conditions in the country of the language being studied. Accounting for these factors is supplemented by the fact that the

development of language and the motives of its studies are largely determined by economic and social development society.

The main goal of teaching foreign languages is communication, that means teaching fluent orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond to various situations.

Presently, the conversation about the search for new pedagogical technologies, methods and means of teaching, which would corresponded to the updated content and standards of education.

New times and conditions require immediate and radical revision both general methodology and specific teaching methods and techniques foreign languages.

The problem of managing educational activities is multifaceted, diverse, has pedagogical, methodical, philosophical, psychological, and other aspects. formed the basis for the development of the modern system language education is formed by economic, political, sociocultural processes. At the university, a special place is occupied by such forms of education, which ensure active participation in the classes of each student, increase knowledge and individual responsibility of students for the results educational work. Pedagogical technologies can successfully solve these tasks.

Formation and development of the student's communicative culture, training practical mastery of foreign languages is the main goal of teaching foreign languages. The task is to create conditions for practical mastering language for each student, choose teaching methods that would allow each student to show their activity, their creativity. Additionally, activating the cognitive activity of the student in the learning process of foreign languages. Learning a foreign language is an effective means of socialization personality, intellectual development of the student, in addition, development of new standards of various forms of activity, focused on the global practice. This fact is of particular important in the study foreign language for special purposes. This course helps to form communicative competence, namely the ability and readiness to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication with native speakers.

Learning a foreign language for special purposes contributes to social adaptation of university students to the conditions of a constantly changing multicultural, multilingual world. First of all, we should mention the fact that intensive study of this subject, expands the linguistic the horizons of students, contributes to their

Intensive technologies in the educational process is closely related to the use of effective techniques and methods teaching, active inclusion of students in the educational process while teaching a foreign language.

Interactive teaching methods using was objective necessity, dictated by the laws of any learning. The creation of foreign language communication in the classroom sets the student to prepare for participation in the process of communication. Learning process, which is a model of the process communication is a base of the intensive method learning. Thus, the intensive teaching method foreign language using interactive methods becomes explanatory principle of building the learning process. Students master correct speech skills, taking into account its phonetic, grammatical, lexical and stylistic aspects while teaching foreign language. Modern education system is implemented by information technology and computer telecommunications usage. Educational institutions are being equipped by powerful computer hardware, community development Internet networks.

The use of interactive methods is closely related to methodological innovation. Interactive method means ability interact or is in the mode of conversation. Due to this fact learning and control process become more productive. In the process of interactive learning a student makes a thoughtful decision, learns think critically. Thus, interactive learning is a special form of cognitive activity organization, which has very specific and predictable goals, monitoring learning outcomes carried out with the help of innovative technologies applicable to predicted expected results.

Information technology education is the technologies, using special technical means (multimedia equipment). When studying theoretical basis intensification of the educational process using interactive teaching methods, it is necessary to rely on information technology. Management of the learning process for the types of speech

activity of the language personality occupies one of the most important places and most strongly tied to the specific conditions of its occurrence and use. This type of work allowed to improve the skills monologue speech, the ability to find the right information, analyzing and drawing conclusions. Messages discussion develops not only skills logical presentation of other people's, but also their own thoughts. It teaches to argue listen and convince the interlocutor. Among the main forms of development of oral speech skills are discussions, round tables, press conferences, and also the development of problem situations for socio-political, country studies and domestic subjects. Problem situations encourage students not only to use ready-made knowledge and skills, but also require them to creatively use the accumulated knowledge, develop the ability to conduct a reasoned dispute, the ability to use acquired knowledge of a foreign language in a dispute. Special attention deserves the use of technical means as a factor of intensification of the process of teaching a foreign language. Their usage opens up completely new, as yet unexplored technological learning options associated with unique capabilities of modern computers and telecommunications. Therefore, the use of various multimedia means of computer technology in system of new information technologies makes it possible individual approach to the organization of educational activities of each student. This is also dictated by the fact that, due to their psychophysiological students have different abilities and inclinations. To achieve the same results in learning a foreign language different students need different amounts of time, exercises for that or other grammatical or lexical material.

Summing up we can consider that the possibility of repeated playback exemplary pronunciation of individual sounds, words, and later sentences in the classroom and outside of class time provides auditory visibility and allows students through conscious imitation to develop the necessary pronunciation and intonation skills. Additionally, we should note the role video materials in a foreign language. As we see, the future is computer technologies in the education system, which will allow comprehensively change and modernize the educational process, taking into account needs of today, to bring them closer to the requirements modernity.

References:

1. Clement, T. Murugavel. English for Employability: A Case Study of the English Language Training Needs Analysis for Engineering Students in India. English Language Teaching; Vol. 8, No. 2; 2015. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v8n2p116>.
2. Djalilova N.D. Learning English as the most important element of professional competence of future doctors. NUU, [1/3/1], 2021.pp.145-148.
3. Djalilova,N., Akhmedova, A., (2020). From the Experience of Applying Innovative Technologies in Teaching Speaking Skills of Medical Students at the English Language Lessons // Bulletin of Science and Practice, №4.422-427.
4. Kuzmina, N. V. Professionalism of the personality of the teacher and the skill of industrial training. Kuzmina. — M.: High school.1990.p.198.
5. M.Jeon. Native-English speaking teacher’s experience in East-Asian language programs. System 88(2020) 102178. www.elsevier.com/locate/system.
6. Sharipova F., Djalilova N. Interactive Learning in the Medical English classroom. Universal Journal of Educational Research, 2020.
7. Yunping Ye. EAP for undergraduate science and engineering students in an EFL context: What should we teach? Ampersand 7 (2020). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.amper.2020.100065>.